

Consequences of weaning and separation for feed intake and milking characteristics of dairy cows in a cow-calf contact system

C.L. van Zyl^{1,2}, H.K. Eriksson³, E.A.M. Bokkers², B. Kemp¹, A.T.M. van Knegsel¹ and S. Agenäs^{3,4}

¹ Adaptation Physiology group, Wageningen University & Research, PO Box 338, 6700 AH Wageningen, the Netherlands

² Animal Production Systems group, Wageningen University & Research, PO Box 338, 6700 AH Wageningen, the Netherlands

³ Department of Applied Animal Science and Welfare, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, PO Box 7024, 750 07 Uppsala, Sweden

⁴ The Beijer Laboratory for Animal Science, Faculty for Vet. Med. and Animal Science, SLU, PO Box 7054, 750 07 Uppsala, Sweden

Corresponding author: Coenraad van Zyl, PO Box 338, 6700 AH Wageningen, the Netherlands, coenraad.vanzyl@wur.nl

Figure S1. Machine milk yield per day, quarter-level milk flow rate, peak milk flow rate and milk electrical conductivity, measured in the milking unit from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of cow and calf after prolonged contact in Exp. 1.

Figure S2. Machine milk yield per day, quarter-level milk flow rate, peak milk flow rate and milk electrical conductivity, measured in the milking unit from 7 d before the start of weaning until 7 d after separation of cow and calf in Exp. 2.

Figure S3.1. Individual cow roughage and concentrate intake per day from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of cow and calf for Exp. 1.

Figure S3.2. Milk yield per day, quarter-level milk flow rate, peak milk flow rate and milk electrical conductivity, measured in the milking unit from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL S1

Figure S1. Machine milk yield (kg) per day (A), quarter-level milk flow rate (kg/min) (B), peak milk flow rate (kg/min) (C) and milk electrical conductivity (mS/cm) (D), measured in the milking unit from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of cow and calf after prolonged contact (-7 to 7 days, where day 0 is the day of separation) in Experiment 1. CONV1 cows ($n = 12$) were conventionally housed cows, separated from their calves within 12h post-partum, and CCC1 cows ($n = 11$) had whole-day cow-calf contact for approximately 8 wk, followed by a system switch to daytime cow-calf contact until abrupt weaning and separation at 16 wk. Dashed lines indicate day of separation (day 0) of cow and calf. Values represent means \pm SEM.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL S2

Figure S2: Machine milk yield (kg) per day (A), quarter-level milk flow rate (kg/min) (B), peak milk flow rate (kg/min) (C) and milk electrical conductivity (mS/cm) (D), measured in the milking unit of all Experiment 2 conventionally housed cows (CONV2, $n = 18$) separated from their calves within 12h post-partum, and cows with whole-day cow-calf contact for 16 wk, after which calves were weaned via nose flaps for 14 d (NF, $n = 10$) or nose flaps for 7 d followed by fence-line contact with the cows for 7 d (NFFL, $n = 9$). The NFFL calves were fitted with nose flaps at the same age as NF calves, but 3 wk later due to the experimental setup. Day 0 was when nose flaps were fitted on the calves, and on day 7 NFFL cows had only fence-line contact with the calves for 7 d (until day 14). On day 14, thus 14 d after the start of the weaning process, all cows and calves were separated. Dashed horizontal line represents the period where fence-line contact between NFFL cows and calves was allowed. Dashed vertical lines indicate the start of weaning (day 0) and day of separation (day 14) of cows and calves. Values represent means \pm SEM.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL S3

Individual roughage and concentrate intake of cows in Experiment 1 per day (Figure S3.1) from 1 wk before until 1 wk after separation, as well as their milking characteristics (Figure S3.2) during the same period. Here cows were not matched on DIM at the time of separation of cow and calf after prolonged cow-calf contact.

Figure S3.1 Individual cow roughage (A) and concentrate (B) intake (kg) per day from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of cow and calf (-7 to 7 d, where day 0 is the day of separation). CONV1 cows were conventionally housed cows and separated from their calves within 12 h after birth, and CCC1 cows had whole-day cow-calf contact for approximately 8 wk, followed by a system switch to daytime cow-calf contact until abrupt weaning and separation at 16 wk. Dashed lines indicate date of separation (day 0) of cow and calf, all cows were moved to a new automatic milking unit on this day. Concentrate intake data of CCC1 cows on day 4 post-separation are missing and thus not presented. Values represent means \pm SEM.

Figure S3.2. Milk yield (kg) per day (A), quarter-level milk flow rate (kg/min) (B), peak milk flow rate (kg/min) (C) and milk electrical conductivity (mS/cm) (D), measured in the milking unit from 7 d before until 7 d after separation of cow and calf after prolonged contact (-7 to 7 days, where day 0 is the day of separation). CONV1 cows were conventionally housed cows, and CCC1 cows had whole-day cow-calf contact for approximately 8 wk, followed by a system switch to daytime cow-calf contact until abrupt weaning and separation at 16 wk. Dashed lines indicate date of separation (day 0) of cow and calf, all cows were moved to a new automatic milking unit on this day. Values represent means \pm SEM.